

Introduction to Machine Learning

Machine Learning

“the process of computers changing the way they carry out tasks by learning from new data, without a human being needing to give instructions in the form of a program” Cambridge dictionary

“study of computer algorithms that can improve automatically through experience and by the use of data. It is seen as a part of artificial intelligence.” Wikipedia

Machine learning

Many approaches for many different tasks

Approaches

- **Supervised learning:** The computer is presented with example inputs and **their desired outputs**, given by a "teacher", and the goal is to learn a general rule that maps inputs to outputs.
- **Unsupervised learning:** **No labels are given** to the learning algorithm, leaving it on its own to find structure in its input. Unsupervised learning can be a goal in itself (discovering hidden patterns in data) or a means towards an end (feature learning).
- ... And anything in between : **reinforcement learning** (self-driving cars..)...

Examples of machine learning

Example of unsupervised learning

Model for the formation of planetary system

Bern model

New metric to quantify the similarity between planetary systems: application to dimensionality reduction using T-SNE★

Y. Alibert

2D representation of
distance between synthetic planetary system

TSNE representation - iteration 1

2D representation of
Distance between synthetic
protoplanetary discs

Clustering + dimension reduction

Bern Model

Examples of reinforcement learning

Supervised learning

Regression task

Classification task

Dog

Cat

Dog

Cat

Cat

Cat

Cat

Cat

Dog

Dog

Cat

Cat

Dog

Dog

Cat

Detection of exoplanets: Transit method

$$\text{Depth} \sim (R_p/R_\star)^2$$

$$S/R = \frac{\text{Depth}}{\sigma_{lc}} \sqrt{N_{transit}}$$

Jupiter transit: flux reduce by 1%
Earth Transit: flux reduce by .008%

Transits: reality

Kepler

river diagram and transit stacking

$$\text{Detection SNR} \propto SNR_{\text{individual}} \sqrt{\frac{\text{Mission duration}}{\text{Orbital period}}}$$

Transit Timing Variations

Effect of TTVs on detection

Detection bias

$$\text{Detection SNR} \propto \frac{SNR_{\text{individual}}}{1 + \frac{\text{TTV amplitude}}{\text{Transit duration}}} \sqrt{\frac{\text{Mission duration}}{\text{Orbital period}}}$$

Finding Star+Period candidates

Kepler-36, $P_{\text{fold}} = 13.8480\text{d}$

asking: **Is there a planet?**

Is the same as asking....

Semantic segmentation with deep learning

Is there a car?

Fence			
Unlabel			

Jeong et al (2018)

Semantic segmentation in RIVERS.deep

Planet-like track?

yes

Photodynamic fit

no

Model architectures

Neuron

$$y = w_1x_1 + w_2x_2 + w_3x_3 + w_4x_4 + w_5x_5 + w_6x_6 + b$$

We can now solve linear problems!

This network is a linear combination of linear functions

$$y = w_1x_1 + w_2x_2 + w_3x_3 + w_4x_4 + w_5x_5 + w_6x_6 + b$$

We need to add non-linearity to the mix

Neuron **transfert function**

For example:
$$A(x) = \begin{cases} 0 & \text{if } x < 0 \\ 1 & \text{otherwise} \end{cases}$$

$$y = A(w_1x_1 + w_2x_2 + w_3x_3 + w_4x_4 + w_5x_5 + w_6x_6 + b)$$

Neuron **transfert** function

Needs to be piecewise derivable!!! (we'll see later why)

(Deep) Neural Network - NN

Convolution filter

$$\begin{pmatrix} -1 & -2 & -1 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 1 & 2 & 1 \end{pmatrix}$$

$$\begin{pmatrix} -1 & 0 & 1 \\ -2 & 0 & 2 \\ -1 & 0 & 1 \end{pmatrix}$$

Convolutional Neural Network - CNN

FC

- car
- truck
- airplane
- ship
- horse

Sample decision tree

Regression task

Sample decision tree

Regression task

Random forest

Supervised ML - performance quantifiers

Supervised training - classification metrics

true/false classifier

		Predicted condition	
		Positive (PP)	Negative (PN)
Total population = P + N			
Actual condition	Positive (P)	True positive (TP), hit	False negative (FN), type II error, miss, underestimation
	Negative (N)	False positive (FP), type I error, false alarm, overestimation	True negative (TN), correct rejection

True positive rate (TPR) or recall = $\frac{TP}{P}$

False positive rate = $\frac{FP}{N}$

wikipedia

$$\text{Accuracy} = \frac{TP + TN}{P + N}$$

Supervised training metrics

multi-class classifier

True positive rate (TPR) or recall = $\frac{TP}{P}$

False positive rate = $\frac{FP}{N}$

CONFUSION MATRIX

Output Class	BRCA	KIRC	LUAD	LUSC	UCEC	
BRCA	342 41.0%	2 0.2%	3 0.4%	4 0.5%	1 0.1%	97.2% 2.8%
KIRC	3 0.4%	211 25.3%	0 0.0%	0 0.0%	0 0.0%	98.6% 1.4%
LUAD	4 0.5%	1 0.1%	54 6.5%	13 1.6%	3 0.4%	72.0% 28.0%
LUSC	2 0.2%	1 0.1%	8 1.0%	79 9.5%	0 0.0%	87.8% 12.2%
UCEC	0 0.0%	0 0.0%	0 0.0%	0 0.0%	104 12.5%	100% 0.0%
	BRCA	KIRC	LUAD	LUSC	UCEC	

Accuracy : trace of the matrix/sum of all elements

Importance of the dataset

wine evaluation without drinking!

- 1.Fixed acidity.
- 2.Volatile acidity.
- 3.Citric acid.
- 4.Residual sugar.
- 5.Chlorides.
- 6.Free sulfur dioxide.
- 7.Total sulfur dioxide.
- 8.Density.
- 9.pH.
- 10.Sulphates.
- 11.Alcohol.
- 12.Quality (score between 0 and 10). **Label**

Need to homogenise the data

Input projection

wine evaluation without drinking!

- A model answering 5, 6 or 7 is right >97% of the time!
- adjust the model to take this into account
- adjust the data-set

Data set creation

Creating new, high quality, datasets is both [hard](#) and [expensive](#).

- Some researchers experiment with training models using [low quality data](#) (weakly supervised learning).
- Amazon offers a [dataset creation service](#) (Amazon Mechanical Turk) where you can pay to get your dataset labelled by humans.

Overfitting : training and validation set

Always split the dataset between:

A training set

A validation set

The model should never see the validation dataset during training.

Overfitting

The model needs to be large enough to perform the task at hand.

The dataset needs to be varied enough cover every possible case of the its future application.

Using too big of a model trained on too little/similar data will result in **over fitting**.

Multi-task learning

Informally, the goal of the multi-task learning is to force the model to use its **computing power** to perform something **meaningful** instead of using it to learn the **noise** of the data (over fitting).

Multi-task learning

detection of cardiovascular diseases

Asking a model to **predict the gender and age** of patient **in addition** to cardiovascular diseases yield strong performance improvements.

Examples of data-augmentation techniques

- insert random fake noise in the data

- use symmetries to generate additional images

Training the network

First forward propagation

here is a image of the patient's retine

Output

-948332

+3112

Does the patient have cardiovascular disease?

The untrained neural network is clueless!

Stochastic Gradient descent

... and hope for convexity....

First, quantify the outputs

Softmax function for classifiers

Special transfert function for the output layer!

Cost functions

Examples

- O is the output vector of the forward propagation
- $T = (0, \dots, 0, 1, 0, \dots, 0)$ is the vector associated to the label of the input.

- Euclidian distance:

- $$C = \sqrt{(O_1 - T_1)^2 + \dots + (O_n - T_n)^2}$$

- Cross Entropy:

- $$C = - [T \cdot \log(O) - (1 - T) \cdot \log(1 - O)]$$

This also need to be piecewise derivable!

Error back-propagation

- We want to estimate how to update the weights of the network to reduce the cost $\Delta W_l = - \frac{\partial C}{\partial W_l}$
- This is done by computing the **back-propagated error** layer by layer, starting from the output layer until the input layer .

Network initialisation

- The back-propagated errors for the layer l go through all layers $l+1 \dots L$
- If the weights are too small, the back-propagated error in the first layers is also small, and vice versa. in big networks you end up with 0s or nans (inf)
- The variance of the weights should be $1/N$ (N Number of weights) so that $\text{var}(y) = \text{var}(x)$

$$y = w_1x_1 + w_2x_2 + w_3x_3 + w_4x_4 + w_5x_5 + w_6x_6 + b$$

Learning rate

- $\Delta W_l = -\frac{\partial C}{\partial W_l}$ is a **local** information on how to reduce the cost.
- New weights: $W_l = W_l - \lambda \Delta W_l$ where λ is the **learning rate**
- The ideal learning rate depend on the problem, and is not necessarily the same for all epoch or all weights (optimisation algorithms)
- Weights can be updated:
 - For every input of the training set '**online learning**'
 - ΔW_l can be first averaged over several inputs '**batch learning**'

Now you should see something like this...

Heading back to exoplanets

Semantic segmentation in RIVERS.deep

Planet-like track?

yes

Photodynamic fit

no

Data generation

10 days

X

Augmentation

Architecture example

Semantic segmentation + classifier

In how many river diagram is there a planet?

Game time!

In how many river diagram is there a planet?

All of them!
Now you have to do this for
4'000 river diagrams
X
200'000 Kepler stars

Semantic segmentation task

Discovering hidden planet

Another example

KOI3184.01

KOI3184.02

RIVERS

$$SNR = \frac{\text{Depth}}{\sigma_{lc}} \sqrt{N_{transit}}$$

Powerful! However **the confidence of a Neural network is not enough for a detection claim!** We had to use a fit of the lightcurve using an MCMC to confirm the detection

input for data fit

Result of the photodynamic fit

TTVs of the system

stacked lightcurve

$$M_b = 4.47^{+0.48}_{-0.43} M_{Earth}, \quad M_c = 5.42^{+0.61}_{-0.57} M_{Earth}$$

$$R_b = 2.03^{+0.12}_{-0.14} R_{Earth}, \quad R_c = 2.05^{+0.14}_{-0.15} R_{Earth}$$